

The Unsaturation and Tautomeric Mobility of Heterocyclic Compounds of the Thiazole Type in Relation to Modern Electronic Conceptions.

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The objects of publishing this paper are twofold. Firstly, it has more than once been suggested to one of us that it would be of considerable advantage to summarise the views which we have expressed at different times during the last six years with regard to the unsaturation and tautomeric mobility of heterocyclic compounds of the thiazole type. Secondly, we wish to take this opportunity to place on record a large variety of experimental data which has been accumulated during these years. As is natural with research work of this kind, it has become necessary to seriously revise many of the speculations which were made in the earlier publications.*

In the first place, the whole gist of the work which has been carried out by us in the last few years has been to emphasise the fact that the relation which thiophen bears to benzene is similarly borne by thiazole to pyridine, and by benzthiazole to quinoline. In the thiazole nucleus, the dominating factor in unsaturation and therefore in chemical reactivity, is the nuclear *nitrogen* atom. The explanation which may be given of this in terms of current electronic theories is shown by the formulæ (I), (II) and (III), in which "aromatic character" is attributed to the formation

* The papers are denoted in the text by the following numbers: (1) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1318; (2) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1488; (3) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2023; (4) Hunter, *ibid.*, p. 2270; (5) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 533; (6) Hunter, *ibid.*, p. 537; (7) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 1385; (8) Hunter, *ibid.*, p. 1401; (9) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2951; (10) Hunter and Soyka, *ibid.*, p. 2958; (11) Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2964; (12) Dyson, Hunter and Morris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 1186; (13) Hunter and Styles, *ibid.*, p. 1209; (14) Hunter and Styles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 3019; (15) Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 458; (16) Hunter and Pride, *ibid.*, p. 943; (17) Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, p. 125; (18) Hunter and Jones, *ibid.*, p. 941; (19) Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, p. 2190.

of a sextuple group (compare Armit and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127**, 1605; Goss and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 1268) on the lines foreshadowed by Bamberger (*Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 1758; 1893, **26**, 1946; *Annalen*, 1893, **273**, 373), and in which each arrow represents a contributing duplet (compare also Ingold, *Annual Reports of the Chemical Society*, 1928, p. 120). Thus, in thiophen the formation of the sextuple group necessitates calling on a lone pair of electrons of the sulphur atom which results in the inertness of this towards bromine, alkyl halides, and similar reagents. In pyridine (II), on the other hand, the sextuple group is completed without calling on the lone pair of electrons of the nitrogen atom which are therefore available for salt formation. Thiazole is therefore to be represented by a formula (III), and it is noteworthy that it is the nuclear sulphur atom which contributes the electrons necessary to the formation of the sextuple group.

(I)

(II)

(III)

It has been shown (17) that the bromination of benzthiazole itself yields a dibromide (IV) in which the labile bromine atoms are considered to be held to the nuclear nitrogen atom by means of semipolar single bonds, after the manner in which Prideaux (*Chem. and Ind.*, 1923, **42**, 672) supposes the labile chlorine atoms to be held to the phosphorus atom in phosphorus pentachloride (V) (compare Ingold and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 1315; Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 1173).

(IV)

(V)

On such a basis, benzthiazole dibromide and the dibromides of the 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles described in this paper therefore become mere analogues of the pentahalides of phosphorus

and antimony, but possess considerable interest in providing examples of the manifestation of valency relationships of this type, occurring in an element of atomic number lower than that of neon. This formulation also enables the octet rule to be maintained, but necessitates abandoning the duplet rule of Lewis.

A singlet linkage must consist of half a covalency and half an electrovalency (Ingold and Ingold, *loc. cit.*). If, therefore, a shared electron is counted as half value for each of the atoms which share it (Lowry, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1923, 18, 285), there should be a positive charge on the nuclear nitrogen atom in the benzthiazole dibromides and an effective half negative charge on each of the labile bromine atoms which are held by singlets. As Sugden has already pointed out (*loc. cit.*), such half charges can be interpreted dynamically on the lines suggested by Hojendahl (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1381) as a statistical average obtained by intergrating the field of the electron in the neighbourhood of a particular atom over a time interval which is large compared with the period of revolution of its orbit.

It may be noted that a formula similar to (IV) was suggested by Thomson (*Phil. Mag.*, 1921, 41, 516) for the hypothetical NCl_5 , and although this compound is evidently incapable of existence, the formation of bromo-addition compounds by pyridines (Trowbridge, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 19, 558) and benzthiazoles suggests the possibility of the existence of a pentafluoride of nitrogen.

Unfortunate difficulties which present themselves in the study of benzthiazole dibromide are, however, the extreme sensitivity of the compound to the atmosphere, and the ease with which it undergoes nuclear substitution in contact with hydroxylic solvents. For the purpose of strengthening the evidence in favour of our view with regard to the constitution of such compounds, it was therefore desirable to prepare stable compounds of this class for the purpose of more detailed examination.

At the same time it was considered of interest to examine more closely the increase in unsaturation accompanying an increase in the atomic volume of the alkyl group in a homologous series of 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles (VI), and attempts were therefore directed towards the preparation of a series of stable 1-alkylaminobenzthiazole dibromides.

The bromination of a series of 1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles (VI, R=Me), synthesised from the corresponding sym-p-tolylalkyl-

thiocarbamides by treatment with bromine under the usual conditions (3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16), was first studied.

The consummate ease with which bromine enters the *ortho*-position to the nuclear nitrogen atom in such bases, however, resulted in the production of *hydrotribromides* of the corresponding 3-bromo-1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles (VII, R=Me, R'=Me, Et, *n*-Pr, and *iso*-C₄H₉).

The bromination of the 3-bromo-1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles (VIII, R=Me) obtained by reduction of the hydrotribromides by sulphurous acid, unfortunately gave rise to gummy bromo-addition products which could not be investigated.

Attention was therefore directed to the 5-chloro-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles (VI, R=Cl) in which it appeared probable that the presence of the *para*-halogen atom would suppress the tendency towards nuclear substitution by bromine (compare Fries, *Annalen*, 1906, 346, 128). Actually, however, the 5-chloro-bases behaved perfectly analogously to the 1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles, and gave rise to *hydrotribromides* of the 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles on bromination in chloroform.

The bromination of the 5-chloro-3-bromo-bases (VIII, R=Cl) yielded a series of stable *dibromides* (IX, R=Cl) of the required type, and a careful study was made of certain of these compounds.

In 1926, it was suggested (9, 10) that on the basis of the modified strain theory of Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 305, 951; compare also Deshapande and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1432; Bains and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1206; Lanfear and Thorpe, *ibid*, p. 2865) it appeared probable that increasing the atomic volume of the alkyl group R in the 1-alkylaminobenzthiazole system (X \rightleftharpoons XI) would increase the stability of the *two-membered* heterocyclic ring N=C, of the aminothiazole phase (X) and thus

enhance this phase of the tautomeric system (compare Packer and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 1203). Consequently on ascending the homologous series of 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles, a gradual shift of equilibrium in favour of the phase (X) would be expected.

The nuclear nitrogen atom of the aminothiazole phase (X) has more residual affinity than the corresponding nitrogen atom of the iminodihydro-phase and hence, on increasing the bulk of the alkyl group R, a corresponding increase in the unsaturation of the thiazole nucleus should ensue, leading to an increase in the stability of the bromo-addition compound of the 1-alkylaminobenzthiazole.

At the time of writing these papers, it was erroneously supposed that the bromo-addition compounds of the 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles obtained from the bromination of *sym.*-arylalkylthiocarbamides in chloroform were *true* benzthiazole bromides (*loc. cit.*), and when qualitative experiments indicated that an increase in "unsaturation" results on ascending a homologous series of 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles, it appeared that confirmation to the hypothesis just outlined had been obtained. It has now been conclusively proved, however, that the bromo-addition compounds obtained by the bromination of arylthiocarbamides in chloroform, are invariably *hydroperbromides* of the corresponding alkylaminobenzthiazoles, and the original suggestions regarding the increase in unsaturation on ascending a homologous series of 1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles must be considered to be invalid.

Nevertheless, it appeared possible that an increase in stability due to the causes elaborated above, might be observed on increasing the volume of the alkyl group in a series of 1-alkylaminobenzthiazole dibromides, and several attempts were therefore made to determine the stability of a series of 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazole dibromides by quantitative methods.

Unfortunately, all attempts to measure the stability of these compounds by hydrolysis, conductivity, and colorimetric methods, proved unsuccessful.

It appeared to us possible, however, that an investigation of the thermal dissociation of the compounds, $\text{NBr}_2 \rightleftharpoons \text{N} + \text{Br}_2$, on the lines on which Ephraim (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1069) has investigated the alkali perhalides, might furnish the desired information. Actually,

however, the alkylaminobenzthiazole dibromides behaved quite differently from the compounds described by Ephraim and betrayed no appreciable dissociation pressure until within about 20° of their melting point, when decomposition commenced rapidly, and proceeded steadily with no evidence of an equilibrium of the type which we had anticipated.

Although the original object of the research was therefore not attained these experiments nevertheless removed any doubt which might be entertained regarding the nature of the benzthiazole dibromides being that of *true compounds*.

Apparent confirmation of an increased tendency for alkylaminobenzthiazoles to form hydroperbromides, was obtained from a study of the bromination of the *sym-o-tolylalkylthiocarbamides*. It was observed that the methyl, ethyl, and *n*-propyl homologues gave rise to *hydrotetrabromides* of the corresponding 1-alkylamino-3-methylbenzthiazoles, whilst *sym-o-tolyl-n-butyl*, *-isobutyl-*, *-n-amyl-*, *-isoamyl-*, *-n-hexyl-*, and *n-heptyl-thiocarbamides* yielded *hydrohexabromides* of the corresponding bases.

The hydrohexabromides in question were strikingly unstable and since it is apparently impossible to obtain absolute evidence that these unstable substances are *not* solid solutions of bromine and a hydroperbromide of a lower order, we prefer not to attempt to base far reaching conclusions on the results of such experiments. It is at least possible, that the production of such complexes is intimately connected with the solubilities of the components concerned.

The problem of the structure of the even-numbered hydroperbromides of the aminobenzthiazoles (3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13) is of considerable importance, because the stability of certain members of the group, such as the hydrodibromide of 1-aminobenzthiazole and the hydrotetrabromide of 1-*p*-toluidino-5-methylbenzthiazole, together with their formation under different conditions, indicates that the substances are *true compounds* (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p.125). The fact that they can be prepared from solutions of the hydrobromides of the bases in inert solvents and bromine (*loc. cit.*) suggests that their structures may contain the hitherto unknown Br_2^{\ominus} and Br_4^{\ominus} ions ; the general formulae of the compounds being, $[\text{Base}, \text{H}] \text{Br}_n^{\oplus}$. On such a basis, the ready elimination of bromine from 1-anilinobenzthiazole hydrotetrabromides with the production of stable hydrotribromides, can be interpreted on the generally accepted view that singlet linkages derive stability from mutual association :

The main difficulty which presents itself in relation to such a hypothesis is, of course, the formulation of the even-numbered hydroperbromides as odd-electron molecules.

Another topic which arises in connection with the hydroperbromides of the aminobenzthiazoles is the observation that the bromination of a single arylthiocarbamide may sometimes give rise to two apparently isomeric forms of the hydroperbromide of the corresponding aminobenzthiazole (7, 10).

At the time when the first observations of this phenomenon were recorded (1926), it was supposed that the bromo-addition compounds in question were true benzthiazole bromides, and it was suggested that they might be derived from the tautomeric forms of the amidine system, and possess structures of the type, $\text{N}[\text{H}]\text{Br}_2:\text{C}:\text{NX}$ and $\text{NBr}_2:\text{C}:\text{N}[\text{H}]\text{X}$. Since it is now known that the bromo-addition compounds in question are hydroperbromides, this hypothesis is obviously invalid. Nevertheless, careful reinvestigation of one of these cases, that of the hydrotribromide of 1-amino-5-methylbenzthiazole (7), confirms the statements which were made by one of us with regard to it nearly five years ago. There *are* two forms of this hydrotribromide, but we have found that on keeping one of them in contact with the liquid phase from which it originally crystallises, that it redissolves, giving a solution from which the second, and more stable, form crystallises. The phenomenon therefore appears to be merely one of a metastable equilibrium of the type which has already been described by Chattaway and Lambert (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1766) in connexion with *p*-bromoacetanilide and 2:4-dibromoacetanilide.

Regarding the possibility of the existence of isomeric hydrobromides (or hydrotribromides) of the type, $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{N}=\text{C}-\text{NH} \\ \ddot{\text{H}} \oplus \end{array} \right] \text{Br}^\ominus$

and $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{NH}-\text{C}=\text{NH} \\ \ddot{\text{H}} \oplus \end{array} \right] \text{Br}^\ominus$, the observation of Burtles and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 362) that both 2:4- and 2:5-diphenylglyoxaline give rise to identical salts indicates that the anions of the tautomers are electromeric. The simplest view, and the one which was suggested to us by Professor Ingold (*private communication*)

is that the positive charge produced by conversion of an amidine into the ammonium condition is located to the extent of about a half charge on each nitrogen atom, just as the negative charge is divided in the carboxylate ion; the ion of asymmetrical triad system being therefore symmetrically constituted quite generally.

A full interpretation of the migration of bromine into the nucleus in a benzthiazole dibromide might therefore be visualised for the case of the 5-chloro-1-amino-compound described in this paper as follows:

A study of the mobility of the symmetrical triad system $[\text{H}]\text{N} \text{---} \text{C}:\text{N} \rightleftharpoons \text{N}:\text{C}:\text{N}[\text{H}]$ in 1-aminobenzthiazoles indicates plainly that the dominating factor is the aromatic character of the heterocyclic nucleus. Bases of this type ($\text{XIV} \rightleftharpoons \text{XV}$, $\text{R} = \text{H}$) methylate almost exclusively on the nuclear nitrogen atom (7, 14, 16, 17, 18) yielding iminomethyl-dihydro derivatives (compare also Young and Crookes, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 59), and it may be noted that Tschitschabin and Konowalowa have recorded similar observations in connexion with the α -aminopyridines (*Ber.* 1921, 54, 814). These facts are clearly capable of interpretation on the basis of the sextuple group theory to which we have already alluded (p. 148). In 1-aminobenzthiazole, for instance, the sextuple group is completed without calling on the lone pair of electrons of the nuclear nitrogen atom which are therefore available for methiodide formation, leading to the production of the hydriodide of 1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole.

Destruction of the aromatic character of the heterocyclic nucleus causes enhanced activity in the iminodihydro-form, resulting in the formation of methylamino-derivatives (Young and Crookes, *loc. cit.* ; compare Forsyth and Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2502).

In a recent investigation (19) a study was made of the effect of polar substituents on the methylation of certain 5-substituted-1-aminobenzthiazoles (XII \rightleftharpoons XIII), in which the *para*-substituent to the nuclear nitrogen atom can act by virtue of electronic displacements, partly similar to those which operate in aromatic substitution (Ingold, Shoppee, and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 1477). It was found that the nitro-, chloro-, bromo-, ethoxy-, and methyl bases (R=NO₂, Cl, Br, OEt, and Me respectively) reacted exclusively in the aromatic phase yielding iminomethyl-dihydro-benzthiazoles.

Particular interest attaches itself to the mobility of 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole (XII \rightleftharpoons XIII, R=F) and we therefore directed our attention to the rational synthesis of this base from *p*-fluoroaniline.

Thiophosgenation of the fluoroaniline gave rise to the corresponding *thiocarbimide*, which yielded *p*-fluorophenylthiocarbamide, on condensation with ammonia ; bromination of this compound under conditions similar to those employed in the case of the chlorine and bromine analogues, gave an excellent yield of the required *fluorobenzthiazole*.

Methylation of 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazoles with methyl sulphate proved to be quite analogous to that of the other 5-substituted-1-aminobenzthiazoles previously investigated (19) ; the only isolable product being 5-fluoro-1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole (XIV). The presence of the isomeric 5-fluoro-1-methylamino-benzthiazole (XV), which was synthesised from *sym-p*-fluorophenylmethylthiocarbamide and bromine, could not be detected in the methylation product.

Now, it has been pointed out by Ingold and Ingold (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 2254) that if considerations relating to the inductive

and directive effects (Ingold and Shaw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, p. 2918 ; Ingold and Vass, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 417) are taken as indicating the electrical states of atoms, the sequence $F > Cl > Br > I$ should connote the order of negativity of halogen substituents in corresponding compounds; in other words, the degree of pre-formation of halide ions. In reactions which involve the separation of a halide ion, however, the actual reactivities of the benzyl halides are in opposite order to that which would be expected from a consideration of the effects of halogens on nuclear substitutions. In view therefore of their suggestion, that the primary condition affecting the reactivity of halogen substituents is not so much the *average* electrical condition of these atoms, but rather the extent to which they are capable of *temporary* electrical polarisation by external fields of reagent molecules, it appeared desirable to examine the behaviour of the remaining 5-halogen--1-aminobenzthiazole ($XVI \rightleftharpoons XVII$, $R = I$) under conditions as closely identical as possible to those employed in the case of the fluorine derivative.

5-Iodo-1-aminobenzthiazole on methylation with methyl sulphate, yielded solely the iminomethyldihydro-*derivative* (XIV, with I in place of F), unaccompanied by the 5-iodo-1-methylamino-*compound* (XV, with I in place of F), which was synthesised from sym-p-iodo-phenylmethylthiocarbamide.

Considerable interest attaches itself to the application of modern electronic theories to the tautomerism of systems, whose mobility depends on the presence of a hydrogen atom and an appropriately situated double bond. The first definite correlation of the behaviour of highly mobile systems of the glutaconic type with the reversible isomeric changes which take place in Fittig's unsaturated acids in the presence of a large concentration of hydroxyl ions, was made by Professor J. F. Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1923, 123, 1361) in an introduction to the series of papers which have been published by Kon and his collaborators on the so-called "three-carbon system." The extension of such principles to other mobile triad systems follows largely as a matter of course.

The application of the general principles of cationotropy (Lapworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1901, 79, 1265 ; Ingold, *Annual Reports of the Chemical Society*, 1927, p. 106) to the amidine system, necessitates that the first condition for mobility should be that the mobile hydrogen atom (proton) first dissociates from the unsaturated molecule, leaving an electromeric anion, $N^{\ominus} - C = NX$, in which tautomeric

electronic displacements $\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{N}}-\overset{\curvearrowright}{\text{C}}=\text{NX}$, bring about a redistribution of the negative charge between the two nitrogen atoms, the eliminated proton having thereby two points of recombination. The complete picture for the tautomerism of the amidine system being

The tendency for an amidine system to come into equilibrium under given conditions should on the basis of this theory, therefore, depend on the stability of the anion in which the actual isomeric change takes place. The *equilibrium* should therefore depend on the stability of the anion $\overset{\ominus}{\text{N}}-\text{C}=\text{NX}$ relative to its isomer, $\text{N}=\text{C}-\overset{\ominus}{\text{NX}}$, and also on the stability of the covalency linkages by means of which the proton is to re-associate with these anions in the $\alpha\beta$ - and $\beta\gamma$ -molecules.

In the three carbon system, $[\text{H}]\text{C}\cdot\text{C}:\text{C}\rightleftharpoons\text{C}:\text{C}\cdot\text{C}[\text{H}]$, present in indene (Ingold and Piggott, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 123, 1470) and in the pentad keto-enol system, $[\text{H}]\text{C}\cdot\text{C}:\text{C}\cdot\text{C}:\text{O}\rightleftharpoons\text{C}:\text{C}\cdot\text{C}[\text{H}]\text{C}:\text{O}$, studied by Kon and Linstead and their pupils (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 616; 1927, pp. 262, 2579; 1928, p. 2343; *et seq.*), there is no doubt that the mobile hydrogen atom is acidic, and that the ability of substituents to promote prototropic change runs more or less parallel with their degree of electron attraction power as deduced from their directive effect in aromatic hydrogen substitutions (Ingold, Shoppee, and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, p. 1477).

An important distinction which is often overlooked in connexion with this correlation of the ability of a group to promote prototropic change with its *meta*-orienting power in benzene substitution (Linstead, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 2498), is that which exists between the *polarisation* of a molecule and its *polarisability*, and we wish to take this opportunity to give emphasis to Shoppee's explanation of the position (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 969). Benzene hydrogen substitutions clearly depend on the negative character of the electrical field at the point of the attaching reagent, whereas tautomeric changes involving a mobile hydrogen atom should on the basis of the cationotropic theory, depend on the positivity of the field at the centre of ionisation. The necessary condition which is required for the former, is one which can arise from the permanent

polarisation of the aromatic molecule due to the electron repulsion of the substituent, or from the molecular *polarisability* of the compound which is enhanced by the presence of substituents containing unshared electrons. In the case of a substituent which attracts electrons, polarisation will have a *deactivating* effect because it causes a decrease of electron availability at the point of the reaction. On the other hand, polarisability due to the presence of a substituent capable of sharing additional aromatic electrons in a molecule in which a free path for electron transference is present, will *not* produce any deactivation because displacements of this type would lead to a recession of electrons from the seat of the reaction. Now the electron recession necessary for the positivity at the field of ionisation on which mobile hydrogen tautomerism is assumed to depend can arise in two ways: (i) from polarisation due to the electron attraction of the substituent, or (ii) from the polarisability which results from the presence of a substituent which is capable of sharing unshared electrons possessed by the system. An electron-repelling substituent will therefore have a retarding influence because it tends to oppose the production of positivity at the point of ionisation, whereas polarisability which results from the presence of a substituent containing unshared electrons which can be shared with the system, will not lead to electron displacements because they would involve electron-accession to the point of ionisation for which, there is no demand.

Retardation of aromatic hydrogen-substitution does not necessarily run parallel with facilitation of prototropy, and therefore an agreement of the type expected by Linstead (*loc. cit.*) for the effect of groups such as, CN, COMe, and CO₂Et, on the mobility of the pentad-keto-enol system and their *meta*-directive power, is not to be anticipated.

The acidity of the simpler amidines, which is sufficient to allow of the formation of definite metallic salts, accords well with the cationotropic theory which we have discussed. On the other hand, it seems a little difficult to reconcile the lack of acidity of semi-cyclic amidines containing a heterocyclic nucleus, of the type we have been studying during the last six years, with the relatively high mobility which they exhibit in the symmetry tests. As has already been pointed out (19), a typical member of the series, such as 1-amino-5-methylbenzthiazole can be heated with sodium in xylene for hours, without any evidence of the formation of a sodio-deriva-

tive of the expected type. It must, of course, be conceded that the polar field offered by this solvent, as indicated by its dielectric constant, is very low, but it is intended to investigate this question more fully at an early date.

Now, the whole of the investigations which have previously been carried out in connexion with the unsaturation and tautomeric mobility of thiazoles, have dealt with benzthiazole and naphthathiazole derivatives. It was therefore of interest to extend the present investigation to certain simple thiazole derivatives, in which the complication of aromatic conjugation from a benzene or naphthalene ring does not arise, and certain preliminary experiments on these lines are included in the experimental portion of this paper.

In the first place it was desirable to investigate the bromination of a typical thiazole base which was free from aromatic substituents, and 2:4-dimethylthiazole (XVI) was chosen for this purpose. This base behaved in quite a different manner from our expectations, however, and gave rise to an unstable *hydropentabromide* of a monobromosubstitution derivative, without any evidence of the formation of a true thiazole bromide. From the properties of this monobromobase which was obtained by reduction of the hydropentabromide with sulphurous acid, there is little doubt that it is 5-bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole (XVIII), and that the hydropentabromide is therefore represented by a formula (XVII).

Attention was next directed to the bromination and methylation of a typical semi-cyclic amidine containing the thiazole ring, and 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (XIX) was chosen for this purpose. In view of the doubt which has been cast by Tcherniac (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1071) on many of Hantzsch's thiazole syntheses from thiocyanacetone (*Annalen*, 1888, 249, 7; compare also Hantzsch and Weber, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 3118), the *p*-toluidinothiazole was rationally synthesised from *p*-tolylthiocarbamide and monochloroacetone. The base obtained in this way answered very closely to the description of the compound given by Hantzsch, although we succeeded in

raising the m.p. of the compound 2 or 3 degrees above that recorded in the literature.

On bromination in chloroform at low temperature, it yielded a beautifully crystalline *hydrotribromide* of a monobromosubstitution derivative. The monobromosubstitution base obtained by reduction with sulphurous acid, is assumed to be 5-bromo-2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (XXI) on account of its non-identity with 2-*o*-bromo-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (XXII), which was synthesised for comparative purposes from *o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide and chloroacetone.

Methylation of 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (XIX) yielded solely 2-*p*-tolylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole (XXIII), which was also synthesised from sym.-*p*-tolylmethylthiocarbamide and mono-chloroacetone. The presence of the isomeric 2-*p*-tolylmethylamino-4-methylthiazole (XXIV) which was prepared from as-*p*-tolylmethylthiocarbamide and chloroacetone, could not be detected in the methylation product. The preferential elimination of hydrogen attached to the NMe-group of the thiocarbamide as water, in conjunction with the hydroxyl group of the enolic form of the chlorinated ketone in the former condensation, seems noteworthy.

This result produces a striking contrast (compare also Young and Crookes, *loc. cit.*) to the behaviour of 1-anilinobenzthiazole, which

yields a mixture of 1-phenylimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole and 1-phenylmethylaminobenzthiazole in the approximate proportion of 2:1, on methylation (19). From the point of view of methylation therefore, the attraction of the aromatic nucleus on the $\alpha\beta$ -double bond is therefore considerably less in the case of the 2-arylamino-thiazoles than in that of the 1-anilinobenzthiazoles.

The suggestion may therefore be offered that a certain degree of the aromatic character of the thiazole nucleus is lost when it is combined with a benzene ring, as in benzthiazole. Since benzthiazole is a dihetero-derivative of naphthalene, this would appear to constitute another example of the mutual effect of aromatic nuclei such as is seen in naphthalene itself, where neither of the presumably identical homocyclic carbon rings exhibits full benzenoid characteristics until one of them is reduced, as in the tetrahydro-derivative (Bamberger, *Annalen*, 1890, 257, 1; compare Challenor and Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2066). This receives support from the bromination experiments described in this paper, since the thiazole derivatives exhibit no apparent tendency towards the formation of addition products, but pass directly into bromo-substitution derivatives, while benzthiazoles tend to yield addition products, prior to nuclear substitution.

If intra-annular tautomeric interchanges of the type which have been postulated by Ingold in the case of the benzene nucleus (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1133, 1143; 1923, 123, 2081), are indeed responsible for the manifestation of the characteristic properties of aromatic compounds, it is clear that they must find their counterpart in heterocyclic compounds of the type of thiophen, pyridine, and thiazole (compare Ingold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 87). It might be anticipated, for instance, that 2:4-dimethylthiazole would possess a dual set of properties in accordance with its double bonded formula (XVI) which follows from its synthesis from thioacetamide and monochloroacetone, and the bridged structure (XXV) which is the analogue of the Dewar phase of the aromatic nucleus.

Actually, however, the experimental investigation of this problem presents great difficulty. It is, for instance, quite out of question to hope to obtain evidence of the two structures from a study of the

regulated oxidation of the base by reagents such as potassium permanganate and potassium ferricyanide, which have been used with such success in the case of the five-carbon intra-annular nucleus (Farmer, Ingold, and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 128) because the attack of the oxidising reagent commences at the sulphur atom (compare Reissert and Manns, *Ber.*, 1928, 61, 1308). Experiments are, however, in progress which have for their object the synthesis of the bridged phase of 2:4-dimethylthiazole (XXIX), although it is anticipated that such a substance would prove to be identical with the dimethylthiazole described in the Experimental.

The facile substitution of bromine for hydrogen on the carbon atom 5 in 2:4-dimethylthiazole is of interest in this connexion, because this is the position which corresponds to that of substitution by bromine in 5-cyclohexanespiro-dicyclo- Δ^2 -penten-3-ol-1-carboxylic acid (XXVI \rightleftharpoons XXVII), in which the cyclohexane ring is assumed to have decreased the stability of the bridge bond in the phase (XXVII) (Ingold and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 320) to the point where it approaches that of the para-bridge in the Dewar phase of the aromatic nucleus (Ingold, Seeley, and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 853).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The Synthesis of 1-Alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles from sym-p-Tolylalkylthiocarbamides and the Conversion of these Bases into the Hydrotribromides of 3-Bromo-1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazoles.—sym-Di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide was prepared in 80–90 % yield by heating a mixture of *p*-toluidine (450 g.), alcohol (600 c.c.), carbon disulphide (700 c.c.), and potassium hydroxide (50 g.) on a steam bath, under an efficient reflux for 3 hours.

p-Tolylthiocarbimide was prepared by heating quantities of 50 g. of the di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide with acetic anhydride (60 c.c.) at the b.p. of the mixture for one minute and pouring the hot liquid into

warm water; the thiocarbimide being isolated by distillation in steam in the usual way. The colourless and highly refractive oil obtained in this way, solidified on cooling to a mass of transparent prisms, which were purified by being melted over anhydrous calcium chloride and distilling the product under reduced pressure. In this way, 200 g. of pure *p*-tolylthiocarbimide, b.p. 140°/34 mm., were obtained from 440 g. of sym-di-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide. When the time of heating with acetic anhydride was allowed to exceed one minute, poor yields were obtained owing to the decomposition of the thiocarbimide into carbonyl sulphide and *p*-acetyltoluidine (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 396).

sym-*p*-Tolylethylthiocarbamide was prepared by adding 10 c.c. of a 33% solution of ethylamine in water to a boiling solution of 10 g. of *p*-tolylthiocarbimide in alcohol (50 c.c.), the mixture being heated for a few minutes at its boiling point. On cooling, the thiocarbamide separated and on recrystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol, formed thin colourless plates, m.p. 97°. (Found: N, 16·3. C₁₀H₁₄N₂S requires S, 16·5 per cent.). Yield: 12 g.

1-Ethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole Hydrotetrabromide.—A suspension of 2 g. of *p*-tolylethylthiocarbamide in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (3·3 c.c. in 15 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath, under reflux, for 15 minutes when hydrogen bromide was copiously evolved. The warm solution was rapidly filtered, cooled in a vacuum desiccator and slightly concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when the hydrotetrabromide crystallised in glistening red needles, which were rapidly dried on porous earthenware in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide. The tetrabromide melted with decomposition at 78°. [Found: Br (total), 62·2; Br (labile), 47·0, C₁₀H₁₂N₂S, HBr(Br₃) requires Br (total), 62·5; Br (labile), 46·9 per cent.].

1-Ethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole.—The bromo-addition compound was suspended in sulphurous acid and treated with sulphur dioxide until reduction was complete; the mixture was basified with ammonia and the ethylaminobenzthiazole was recrystallised from methyl alcohol. The base formed colourless flat prisms, m.p. 129°. (Found: S, 16·3. C₁₀H₁₂N₂S requires S, 16·7 per cent.).

Bromination.—A solution of 2 g. of the ethylaminobenzthiazole in chloroform (30 c.c.) was treated with bromine (3·3 c.c. in 10 c.c. of chloroform), and the solution was kept. 3-Bromo-1-ethyl-

amino-5-methylbenzthiazole hydrotribromide crystallised in yellow needles which had m.p. 147° (darkening with sintering at 130-40°), after being dried in a vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 62·6; Br (labile), 32·0. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 62·5; Br (labile), 31·3 per cent.]. *3-Bromo-1-ethylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole* obtained either by reduction of the hydrotribromide with sulphurous acid, or by boiling this bromo-addition compound with alcohol, separated from ethyl acetate in prisms, m.p. 150°. (Found: Br, 29. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 29·5 per cent.).

sym-p-Tolyl-n-propylthiocarbamide.—*n*-Propylamine (8 c.c.) in water (25 c.c.) was added to a hot solution of *p*-tolylthiocarbimide (10 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) and the mixture was heated for a few minutes on a steam-bath. The *propylthiocarbamide* separated on cooling, and a further quantity was obtained by working up the mother-liquors. On recrystallisation from dilute alcohol, the thiocarbamide formed colourless plates, m.p. 70°. (Found: S, 15·6. $C_{11}H_{16}N_2S$ requires S 15·4 per cent.). Yield: 13 g.

1-n-Propylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole Hydrotetrabromide.—A solution of 2 g. of the propylthiocarbamide in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (3·1 c.c. in 15 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. The *hydrotetrabromide* crystallised in small orange needles which were dried in a vacuum; m.p. 61°. (Found: Br, 61·1. $C_{11}H_{14}N_2S, HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br, 60·8 per cent.). *1-n-Propylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole* separated from methyl alcohol in transparent flat, hexagonal prisms, m.p. 116°. (Found: S, 15·3. $C_{11}H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 15·5 per cent.).

3-Bromo-1-n-propylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole Hydrotribromide.—A solution of bromine (3·1 c.c.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was added to 2 g. of the *n*-propylaminobenzthiazole in the same solvent (26 c.c.) and the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. An unstable, red, hydroperbromide separated, which decomposed yielding the *hydrotribromide*, on being kept in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide overnight. This hydrotribromide formed yellow prisms, m.p. 130° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 60·4; Br (labile), 30·6. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2BrS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 60·8; Br (labile), 30·4 per cent.].

3-Bromo-1-n-propylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole separated from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 116°. (Found: Br, 28·3. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 28·1 per cent.).

sym-p-Tolylisobutylthiocarbamide, prepared from the tolylthiocarbimide and isobutylamine, separated from dilute methyl alcohol

in glistening plates, m.p. 87°. (Found: S, 14.5. $C_{12}H_{18}N_2S$ requires S, 14.4 per cent.).

1-isoButylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole Hydrotribromide.—A solution of the *isobutylthiocarbamide* (2 g.) in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (2 c.c. in 15 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 15 minutes. Concentration of the solution in *vacuo* yielded orange-yellow plates of the *hydrotribromide* of the *butylaminobenzthiazole*, m.p. 89° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 52.3; Br (labile), 31.3. $C_{12}H_{16}N_2S, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 52.3; Br (labile), 34.7 per cent.].

1-isoButylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole crystallised from methyl alcohol in stellate clusters of thin oblong prisms, m.p. 132°. (Found: S, 14.1. $C_{12}H_{16}N_2S$ requires S, 14.5 per cent.).

3-Bromo-1-isobutylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole Hydrotribromide, prepared by concentrating the solution obtained from the *butylaminobenzthiazole* (2 g.), chloroform (30 c.c.) and bromine (2.9 c.c.), under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, formed yellow prisms, m.p. 126° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 59.1; Br (labile), 30.9. $C_{12}H_{15}N_2BrS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 59.3; Br (labile), 29.7 per cent.].

3-Bromo-1-isobutylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole crystallised from methyl alcohol in prisms, m.p. 95°. (Found: S, 27.0. $C_{12}H_{15}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 26.8 per cent.).

Bromination of p-Tolylthiocarbamide.—A suspension of 2 g. of *p-tolylthiocarbamide* in chloroform (15 c.c.) was treated with bromine (4 c.c. in 15 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath, under reflux, for 15 minutes. On cooling the solution in a vacuum, deep red crystals of a highly unstable substance separated, whose m.p. could not be determined on account of its rapid decomposition. (Found: Br, 65.1. $C_8H_8N_3SBr(Br_3)$ requires Br, 66.1 per cent.). On keeping in a vacuum, this substance yielded the orange-yellow *hydrotribromide*, m.p. 108-109° (sintering at 100°) already recorded (Hunter, *loc. cit.*). (Found: Br, 59.5. Calc. Br, 59.2 per cent.). If, however, the deep red crystals first obtained were allowed to remain in contact with the mother-liquor for several hours, exposed to moist laboratory air, they redissolved and the liquid subsequently deposited deep orange-red crystals of the *second form* of the *hydrotribromide*, m.p. 133°. [Found: Br (total) 59.6; Br (labile), 39.7. Calc. Br (total), 59.2; Br (labile), 39.5 per cent.].

The Synthesis of 5-Chloro-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles from sym-p-Chlorophenylalkylthiocarbamides: the Conversion of these Bases into Hydroperbromides of the 5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazoles, and the Preparation of a Series of 5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-alkylaminobenzthiazole Dibromides.—Several methods of preparation of *p*-chloroacetanilide have been described in the literature, but in all cases the yields are poor. We are indebted to Professor R. W. West for the following method of preparation, which was used in connexion with the present investigation.

A solution of 400 g. of acetanilide in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (150 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (500 c.c.) was cooled to 0° in a large enamelled pan, surrounded by an efficient freezing mixture. The filtrate obtained from shaking a mixture of 600 g. of bleaching powder with water (4000 c.c.) at intervals of a period of time greater than an hour, was then added gradually to the cooled mixture, which was mechanically stirred during the addition, which occupied several hours. The temperature of the chlorination was kept below 5°, and the white crystals which separated were collected and dried at 100°. The yield of crude *p*-chloroacetanilide was 225 g.

A mixture of this product (450 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (1200 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 2 hours, cooled, and neutralised with anhydrous sodium carbonate; the *p*-chloroaniline was isolated by distillation in steam, when it formed a colourless oil which solidified on cooling. Yield: 265 g.

sym-Di-*p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide was prepared by heating a mixture of *p*-chloroaniline (365 g.), carbon disulphide (700 c.c.), alcohol (600 c.c.), and sulphur (20 g.) (compare Hegershoff, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2245) under reflux for 3 hours. Yield: 400 g.; m. p. 171°.

p-Chlorophenylthiocarbimide was prepared in 80% yield by heating quantities of 100 g. of *sym*-di-*p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide with acetic anhydride (110 c.c.) under reflux, for 30 minutes, pouring the mixture into hot water and isolating the thiocarbimide by distillation in steam. The *p*-chlorophenylthiocarbimide distilled over as a colourless oil, which solidified on cooling. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol it formed slender white needles, m. p. 45°, having a pronounced aniseed-like odour.

In connexion with the present investigation, we found that 3.1 kg. of acetanilide gave 250 g. of *p*-chlorophenylthiocarbimide; the over-all yield for the process is therefore only 6.4 per cent.

The 5-chlorobenzthiazoles were prepared on lines similar to those described in connexion with the 1-alkylamino-5-methylbenzthiazole derivatives.

5-Chloro-1-aminobenzthiazole Hydrodibromide.—This compound, previously described as a dibromide by Dyson, Hunter, and Morris (12), was prepared by bromination of a suspension of 2 g. of *p*-chlorophenylthiocarbamide in chloroform (15 c.c.) with bromine (3.4 c.c. in 15 c.c. of the same solvent). It formed aggregates of silky, red-brown needles, which lost bromine at 80-90°, showed softening at 130° and melted with charring at 230-235°. [Found: Br (total), 45.9; Br (labile), 24.0. Calc. for $C_7H_5N_2ClS, HBr(Br)$: Br (total), 46.4; Br (labile), 23.2 per cent.].

Bromination of 5-Chloro-1-aminobenzthiazole.—A suspension of 2 g. of the 5-chloro-1-amino-base in chloroform (50 c.c.) was treated with bromine (3.4 c.c. in 15 c.c. of the same solvent), and the liquid was rapidly filtered and kept in an evacuated desiccator, when silky orange needles, having the composition of a *dibromide* separated, m. p. 82-83°. (Found: Br, 46.7. $C_7H_5N_2Br_2S$ requires Br, 46.4 per cent.). Attempts to dissolve this bromo-addition compound in chloroform resulted in a rapid discharge of colour, accompanied by conversion into the *hydrobromide* of 5-chloro-3-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole (compare Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 127). When the bromo-addition compound was added to a mixture of chloroform and potassium iodide solution in water, acidified with acetic acid, and the mixture was shaken, an appreciable liberation of iodine was observed. *5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole* separated from ethyl acetate in small needles, m. p. 245°. (Found: Br, 30.2. $C_7H_4N_2ClBrS$ requires Br, 30.4 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-aminobenzthiazole Dibromide.—A solution of the base in the minimum quantity of warm chloroform was treated with excess of bromine, and the solution was allowed to cool gradually, when the *dibromide* crystallised. This bromo-addition compound was collected, washed with a little chloroform and dried overnight in a vacuum. It formed glistening golden plates, which showed loss of bromine at 160°, but were unmelted at 280°. [Found: Br (total), 56.5; Br (labile), 37.4. $C_7H_4N_2ClBrS(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 56.7; Br (labile), 37.8 per cent.].

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-methylaminobenzthiazole Hydrotribromide.—A suspension of 1 g. of 5-chloro-1-methylaminobenzthiazole (19) in 30 c.c. of chloroform was treated with bromine (1.6 c.c. in 15 c.c. of

chloroform). The bromo-addition compound formed glistening orange plates, m. p. 270° (with charring; loss of bromine at 200°). (Found: Br, 61.9. $C_8H_7N_2ClBrS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br, 61.7 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-methylaminobenzthiazole separated from ethyl acetate-chloroform in feathery white needles, m. p. 180° . (Found: Br, 29.0. $C_8H_6N_2ClBrS$ requires Br, 28.8 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-methylaminobenzthiazole dibromide, prepared as in the case of the amino-compound, formed small yellow plates, which charred without melting at 250° . [Found: Br (total), 55.2; Br (labile), 36.5. $C_8H_6N_2ClBrS(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 54.9; Br (labile), 36.6 per cent.].

sym-p-Chlorophenylethylthiocarbamide.—A hot solution of *p*-chlorophenylthiocarbimide (10 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) was treated with 10 c.c. of a 33% aqueous solution of ethylamine, and the mixture was boiled for one minute and then cooled. On re-crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol, the thiocarbamide formed slender needles, m.p. 119° . (Found: Cl, 16.4; S, 14.9. $C_9H_{11}N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 16.6; S, 14.9 per cent.). Yield: 12 g.

5-Chloro-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole hydrotetrabromide was prepared by heating *sym-p*-chlorophenylethylthiocarbamide (2 g.) in chloroform (15 c. c.) with bromine (3 c. c.) for 15 minutes; the solution was filtered hot and cooled in an evacuated desiccator, when the *hydrotetrabromide* crystallised in deep red prisms, m. p. $64-66^{\circ}$ (softening at 58°). [Found: Br (total), 60.0; Br (labile), 46.0. $C_9H_9N_2ClS, HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br (total), 60.1; Br (labile) 45.1 per cent.]. *5-Chloro-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole* separated from methyl alcohol in prisms, m. p. 159° . (Found: Cl, 16.8; S, 15.3. $C_9H_9N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 16.7; S, 15.1 per cent.). *5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide*, prepared by adding bromine (3 c.c. in 15 c.c. of chloroform) to a solution of the 5-chloro-1-ethylamino-base (2 g.) in chloroform (50 c.c.), formed microscopic yellow prisms, m. p. $181-83^{\circ}$ (decomp. with charring). [Found: Br (total), 60.1; Br (labile), 31.0. $C_9H_8N_2ClBrS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 60.1; Br (labile), 30.1 per cent.].

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole crystallised from ethyl alcohol in long, slender needles, m. p. 155° . (Found: Br, 27.1. $C_9H_8N_2ClBrS$ requires Br, 27.4 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-ethylaminobenzthiazole dibromide formed yellow needles, m. p. 190° . [Found: Br (total), 58.7; Br (labile), 35.5. $C_9H_8N_2ClBrS(Br)$ requires Br (total), 53.2; Br (labile), 35.4 per cent.]

sym-p-Chlorophenyl-n-propylthiocarbamide crystallised in slender needles, m. p. 110°. [Found: Cl, 15.4; S, 14.1. $C_{10}H_{13}N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 15.5; S, 14.0 per cent.)

5-Chloro-1-n-propylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide, prepared in the usual way, crystallised in small red prisms, m. p. 87°. (Found: Br, 58.5. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2ClS, HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br, 58.5 per cent.)

5-Chloro-1-n-propylaminobenzthiazole crystallised in prisms, m. p. 123°. (Found: Cl, 15.8; S, 14.3. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 15.7; S, 14.1 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-n-propylaminobenzthiazole hydrotribromide formed small yellow prisms, m. p. 191° (sintering at 185°). (Found: Br, 58.7. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2ClBrS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br, 58.6 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-n-propylaminobenzthiazole separated from ethyl acetate in needles, m. p. 190°. (Found: Br, 26.3. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2ClBrS$ requires Br, 26.2 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-n-propylaminobenzthiazole dibromide formed yellow prisms, m. p. 173°. [Found: Br (total), 52.0; Br (labile), 33.8. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2ClBrS(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 51.5; Br (labile), 34.4 per cent.]

sym-p-Chlorophenylisobutylthiocarbamide crystallised from dilute methyl alcohol in small glistening plates, m. p. 122°. (Found: Cl, 14.4; S, 13.5. $C_{11}H_{15}N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 14.7; S, 13.2 per cent.)

5-Chloro-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole Hydrotribromide.—The mixture obtained from *sym-p-chlorophenylisobutylthiocarbamide* (2 g. in 15 c.c. of chloroform) and bromine (2.6 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) was heated for 15 minutes and cooled in an evacuated desiccator after rapid filtration. The *hydrotribromide* crystallised in glistening orange-red plates, m. p. 101° (softening at 95-97°). [Found: Br (total), 49.7; Br (labile), 34.3. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2ClS, HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 49.8; Br (labile), 33.2 per cent.]

5-Chloro-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole separated from methyl alcohol in needles, m. p. 138°. (Found: Cl, 15.1; S, 13.5. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 14.8; S, 13.3 per cent.). The bromination of this isobutyl-amino-base under the usual conditions. gave rise to a *perbromide* having the composition required for a *hydropentabromide* of *5-chloro-3-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole*; m. p. 168°. (Found: Br, 66.8. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2ClBrS, HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br, 66.6 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole crystallised from methyl alcohol in white prisms, m. p. 93°. (Found: Br, 25.3. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2ClBrS$ requires Br, 25.0 per cent.)

5-Chloro-3-bromo-1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole dibromide formed glistening golden plates, m.p. 265° (softening at 195°). [Found: Br (total), 50.2; Br (labile), 32.9. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2ClBrS(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 50.0; Br (labile), 33.4 per cent.].

Stability Experiments. (i) Volumetric Method.—A solution of the dibromide in chloroform was slowly hydrolysed by acetic acid containing a small quantity of water. At definite intervals, quantities of 25 c.c. of the liquid were withdrawn, run into 25 c.c. of *N*/10-silver nitrate, the liquid diluted to 150 c.c., and titrated with standard ammonium thiocyanate after acidification with nitric acid. Some difficulty was experienced in connexion with the end point, owing to the colour of the bromide solution. In later experiments, the chloroform was extracted with water and the Br' ion estimated by the Fischer-Volhard method. This method also failed, owing to the action of the hypobromous acid on the indicator, and the low solubility of the bromides which necessitated the estimation of small concentrations of Br' ion in a large volume of liquid.

(ii) Gravimetric Method.—A solution of exactly 0.0025 g. of the dibromide in 150 c.c. of dry chloroform was maintained at 29.5° in a thermostat and 25 c.c. of acetic acid containing 1 per cent. of water, were added. At given intervals of time, 50 c.c. of the liquid were withdrawn by means of a pipette, thrice extracted with 200 c.c. of water and the united extracts were treated with 5 c.c. of sulphurous acid to destroy hypobromous acid present. The solution obtained in this way was then acidified with nitric acid, and the Br' ion estimated gravimetrically in the usual way.

The method was unsuccessful, due to the process of extraction with water which carried the hydrolysis to completion. Several reagents were therefore investigated from the point of view of removing unchanged benzthiazole dibromide without liberation of hydrogen bromide (ethylene, amyl alcohol, etc.), but they were found to give products which were appreciably hydrolysed under the experimental conditions.

(iii) Colorimetric Method.—It was observed that solutions of the dibromides are usually orange in colour when freshly prepared, but become paler in intensity during hydrolysis. The hydrolysis experiments with acetic acid containing 1 per cent. of water at 29.5° described in the previous section, were therefore repeated, the hydrolysing solution being removed at definite intervals and examined by means of a simple type of nephelometer, consisting of two graduated tubes

illuminated by blue light. One cylinder containing the standard solution was compared with the other tube containing a given volume of the reaction mixture which had been kept at the standard temperature in the thermostat ; the observations being made by adjustment of the height of the standard column. Unfortunately, it was found that a small amount of red colouring matter was produced (by oxidation) during the hydrolysis of the dibromides, which masked the discharge of colour of the bromo-addition compound. The nature of these red coloured oxidation products has not yet been established but they are readily obtained by prolonged boiling of alcoholic solutions of the dibromides.

(iv) *Conductivity Method*.—During the hydrolysis of the dibromides, Br' ion is produced, and the course of the reaction should therefore be capable of being studied by observations on the change of electrical conductivity of the reaction mixture. The technique of the hydrolysis experiments in this case was the same as that employed in the previous experiments ; portions of the reaction mixture being removed at definite intervals of time and examined in a conductivity cell. Actually, however, our experiments showed that the change in conductivity was so small that it could not be determined with any accuracy with the apparatus at our disposal, and furthermore, the platinum electrodes of the conductivity cell become coated with a yellow deposit, which interfered with the investigation.

(v) *Dissociation Method*.—The details of this method and the general experimental technique have already been described by Ephraim (*loc. cit.*). We found it convenient to replace the large sulphuric acid bath by means of an electrical resistance furnace, using a platinum thermometer to surround the bulbs ; the thermometer being calibrated before each determination. In the cases of the ethylamino- and the isobutylamino-benzthiazole dibromides, which were the particular compounds studied in this connexion, thermal dissociation was inappreciable until within about 20° of the melting point of the compounds, when bromine was rapidly and continuously evolved, without any indication of a possible equilibrium of the type which we had anticipated.

The Bromination of the sym-o-Tolylalkylthiocarbamides and the Hydroperbromides of the 1-Alkylamino-3-methylbenzthiazoles.

The bromination of sym-o-tolylmethyl-, and sym-o-tolyl-n-propylthiocarbamides has already been described ; both of these thiocarb-

mides yield unstable hydrotetrabromides of the corresponding 1-alkylamino-3-methylbenzthiazoles (14).

sym-o-Tolylethylthiocarbamide.—A solution of *o*-tolylthiocarbimide in alcohol was treated with 20 per cent. excess of ethylamine, the solution was then boiled for a minute or two, cooled, and concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. On recrystallisation from absolute alcohol, the thiocarbamide formed colourless prisms, m.p. 90°. (Found: S, 16·7. $C_{10}H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 16·5 per cent.).

Bromination.—A suspension of the ethylthiocarbamide (2 g.) in chloroform (12 c.c.) was treated with bromine (2 c.c. in 3 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 10 minutes, cooled, and concentrated in a vacuum, when the *hydrotetrabromide* of 1-ethylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole separated in small orange-yellow prisms, which were rapidly dried in a vacuum before analysis, m.p. 78° (effervescence at 140°). (Found: Br, 62·1. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2S, HBr(Br_3)$ requires Br, 62·5 per cent.).

1-*Ethylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole* was obtained by suspending the hydrotetrabromide in sulphurous acid and treating it with sulphur dioxide until all solid matter was quite colourless; the mixture being basified with ammonia (*d* 0·880). The base crystallised from ethyl acetate in white needles, m.p. 114°. (Found: S, 16·5. $C_{10}H_{12}N_2S$ requires S, 16·7 per cent.).

sym-o-Tolyl-n-butylthiocarbamide, crystallised on keeping in an evacuated desiccator, and separated from alcohol in prisms, m.p. 53°. (Found: S, 14·1. $C_{12}H_{18}N_2S$ requires S, 14·4 per cent.).

Bromination.—A solution of the *n*-butylthiocarbamide (2 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (2 c.c.) as in the case of the ethyl compound. Concentration of the solution under reduced pressure yielded a highly unstable substance, having the composition required by that of a *hydrohexabromide* of 1-*n*-butylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole, which crystallised in small red needles, m. p. 61° (sintering at 55°), which were very rapidly dried on porous earthenware in vacuum, and *immediately* analysed with all the precautions used by Dyson, Hunter, and Soyka (15) in connexion with the unstable hydropentabromide of 5:4'-dibromoanilinobenzthiazole. This red perbromide was so unstable that it commenced to decompose with loss of bromine within 10 minutes. (Found: Br, 68·0. $C_{12}H_{16}N_2SHBr(Br_5)$ requires Br, 68·6 per cent.).

1-*n-Butylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole*, obtained by concentrating a solution of the gum obtained reduction of the hydrohexabro-

mide, in dilute methyl alcohol under reduced pressure, at laboratory temperature, formed colourless prisms, m. p. 50° (Found: S, 14.2. $C_{12}H_{16}N_2S$ requires S, 14.5 per cent.).

sym-o-Tolyisobutylthiocarbamide formed colourless prisms, m. p. 68° . (Found: S, 14.6 per cent.).

Bromination.—The unstable bromo-addition compound obtained from the isobutylthiocarbamide had the composition of a *hydrohexamide* of the 1-isobutylaminobenzthiazole, and formed red prisms, m. p. $70-72^{\circ}$ (sintering at 60°). (Found: Br, 67.8 per cent.).

1-isoButylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole separated from dilute methyl alcohol in short needles, m. p. 58° . (Found: S, 14.7 per cent.):

sym-o-Tolyl-n-amylthiocarbamide, prepared from the tolylthiocarbamide and *n*-amylamine, formed large colourless prisms, m. p. 74° . (Found: S, 13.8. $C_{13}H_{20}N_2S$ requires S, 13.6 per cent.).

Bromination.—A solution of the *n*-amylthiocarbamide (2 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (2 c.c. in 3 c.c. of the same solvent); the *hydrohexabromide* formed silky orange-red needles, which rapidly decomposed leaving a yellow residue of a lower bromo-addition compound: m. p. 61° (sintering at 55°). (Found: Br, 66.4. $C_{13}H_{15}N_2SHBr(Br_5)$ requires Br, 67.2 per cent.).

1-*n*-Amylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole separated from dilute methyl alcohol in white prisms, m. p. 48° . (Found: S, 13.9. $C_{13}H_{28}N_2S$ requires S, 13.7 per cent.).

sym-o-Tolylisoamylthiocarbamide, prepared from isoamylamine, formed small white prisms, m. p. 57° . (Found: S, 13.1 per cent.).

1-isoAmylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole *hydrohexabromide*, prepared as in the case of the *n*-amyl derivative from 2 g. of *sym-o*-tolyl-isoamylthiocarbamide, separated in glistening red needles, m. p. 57° (sintering at 50°). (Found: Br, 66.8 per cent.). This compound decomposed turning yellow with loss of bromine, on keeping for 10 minutes.

1-isoAmylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole.—The gum obtained by reduction of the hydrohexabromide, followed by basification with ammonia, crystallised with some difficulty from dilute methyl alcohol in small white crystals, m. p. 59° . (Found: S, 13.8 per cent.).

sym-o-Tolyl-n-hexylthiocarbamide, prepared by condensation of the tolylthiocarbimide with *n*-hexylamine, formed small white prisms, m. p. 76° . (Found: S, 13.2. $C_{14}H_{22}N_2S$ requires S, 12.8 per cent.).

1-*n*-Hexylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole *hydrohexabromide*, prepared from 2 g. of the hexylthiocarbamide, chloroform (13 c.c.), and bromine (2 c.c.), formed brilliant red needles, m.p. 58° (sintering

at 55°). (Found: Br, 65·2. $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$, $HBr(Br_5)$ requires S, requires Br, 65·9 per cent.)

1-n-Hexylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole separated from dilute alcohol in long needles, m. p. 46°. (Found: S, 13·0. $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$ requires S, 12·9 per cent.)

For the benefit of any future investigators, it may be stated here that the 1-alkylamino-3-methylbenzthiazole field presents considerable experimental difficulty. Both the sym-*o*-tolylalkylthiocarbamides and 1-alkylamino-3-methylbenzthiazoles, from *n*-butyl onwards, form low melting solids which usually separate from their solutions in the form of tenacious gums, which frequently present considerable difficulty in recrystallisation. The hydroperbromides of the bases in addition to this, are most unstable and decompose under the ordinary conditions of drying in an evacuated desiccator. Indeed, concordant values for the analysis of these unstable bromo-addition compounds can only be obtained by careful and very rapid drying in a vacuum, followed by the immediate analysis. In the experiments just described the bromo-addition compounds were kept out of contact of the atmosphere until the actual moment of weighing.

The Methylation of 5-Fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole and of 5-Iodo-1-aminobenzthiazole. (i) *Synthesis of 5-Fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole from p-Fluoroaniline.*—(A) *p-Fluorophenylthiocarbimide.* Thiocarbonyl chloride (1 mol.) was completely suspended in cold water (10 vols.) by vigorous stirring during the addition of *p*-fluoroaniline (0·75 mol.), dissolved in chloroform (5 vols.). After half hour's stirring, the chloroform layer was removed and dried with calcium chloride and the solvent and excess of thiocarbonyl chloride were removed by evaporation on a steam-bath. The *fluorophenylthiocarbimide* obtained by fractionation of the residue, formed a refractive oil, b. p. 228°/760 mm. (Found: S, 21·3. C_7H_4NFS requires S, 20·9 per cent.). Yield: 70-80%. (B) *p-Fluorophenylthiocarbamide*, prepared by treating an alcoholic solution of the thiocarbimide with excess of ammonia (d 0·880) and warming the solution on a water-bath, crystallised from alcohol in glistening needles, m. p. 164°. (Found: S, 19·3. $C_7H_7N_2FS$ requires S, 18·9 per cent.). (C) *Bromination.* *p*-Fluorophenylthiocarbamide (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c. in 1 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 10-15 minutes and cooled. The bromo-addition compound obtained in this way, was suspended in sulphur-

ous acid and treated with sulphur dioxide until reduction was complete. On basification and recrystallisation from alcohol, 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole was obtained in small white plates, m. p. 182°. (Found: S, 18·8. $C_7H_5N_2FS$ requires S, 19·0 per cent.).

5-Fluoro-1-acetaminobenzthiazole obtained by heating a solution of the fluoro-base in acetic anhydride for a few minutes, diluting the solution with alcohol and concentrating the mixture on a steam-bath crystallised from alcohol-ethyl acetate in white plates, m. p. 221°. (Found: S, 15·6. $C_9H_7ON_2FS$ requires S, 15·3 per cent.).

Methylation of 5-Fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole and the Synthesis of 5-Fluoro-1-methylaminobenzthiazole by way of sym-p Fluorophenylmethylthiocarbamide.—(A) 4 c.c. of methyl sulphate were added to a solution of 1 g. of 5-fluoro-1-aminobenzthiazole in alcohol (10 c.c.) and the solution was heated on a steam-bath under reflux; 2 g. of potassium hydroxide were then added. The mixture was diluted with 100 c.c. of water, kept for 30 minutes, and then extracted with chloroform. The gum obtained by removal of the chloroform could not be crystallised. It was therefore acetylated by treatment with excess of hot acetic anhydride, followed by dilution with alcohol; the solution being thereafter concentrated on a steam-bath. The product which consisted of 5-fluoro-1-acetimino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole (m. p. 190°), had m. p. 197° after several recrystallisations from alcohol. (Found: S, 14·6. $C_{10}H_9ON_2FS$ requires S, 14·3 per cent.). A careful search of the mother-liquors failed to reveal the presence of the isomeric 5-fluoro-1-acetylmethylaminobenzthiazole, which was rationally synthesised as described below.

(B). sym-p-Fluorophenylmethylthiocarbamide was prepared by adding excess of an aqueous solution of methylamine (33%) to a solution of the fluorophenylthiocarbimide in alcohol. It formed a conglomerate mass of brownish waxy needles, m. p. 70°. (Found: S, 17·2. $C_8H_9N_2FS$ requires S, 17·4 per cent.).

5-Fluoro-1-methylaminobenzthiazole.—The fluorophenylmethylthiocarbamide (0·5 g.) in chloroform (6 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·4 c.c.) and the mixture was heated under reflux, and the bromo-addition compound was reduced with sulphurous acid. The methylamino-base crystallised from alcohol in white prisms, m.p. 174°. (Found: S, 17·6 per cent.). The acetyl derivative, prepared by acetylation with acetic anhydride, crystallised from alcohol—ethyl acetate in needles, m. p. 156°. (Found: S, 14·4. $C_{10}H_9ON_2FS$ requires S, 14·3 per cent.).

(ii) *Synthesis of 5-Iodo-1-aminobenzthiazole.*—5-Iodo-1-aminobenzthiazole was prepared by bromination of *p*-iodophenylthiocarbamide in chloroform under conditions similar to those used in connexion with the fluoro-derivative. It crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 210°. (Found: S, 11·8. $C_7H_5N_2IS$ requires S, 11·6 per cent.).

Methylation.—A mixture of 5-iodo-1-aminobenzthiazole (1 g.), methyl sulphate (4 c.c.) and alcohol (10 c.c.) was heated on a steam-bath under reflux for 10 minutes. Solid potassium hydroxide (2 g.) was then added to the mixture, which was diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. Removal of the chloroform yielded a gum, which was dissolved in acetone and treated with a solution of 2 g. of picric acid in the same solvent, when the *picrate* of 5-iodo-1-imino-2-methyl-1:2-dihydrobenzthiazole separated (1·5 g.) in the form of short yellow prisms, which were fairly soluble in acetone, m. p. 222°. (Found: S, 6·4. $C_8H_7N_2IS$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires S, 6·3 per cent.). The presence of the *picrate* of the isomeric methyl-amino-base (m. p. 245°) could not be detected.

Synthesis of 5-Iodo-1-methylaminobenzthiazole.—*sym-p-Iodophenylmethylthiocarbamide*, prepared from *p*-iodophenylthiocarbimide and methylamine in alcohol, crystallised in needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: S, 11·3. $C_8H_9N_2IS$ requires S, 10·9 per cent.). *5-Iodo-1-methylaminobenzthiazole*, prepared by bromination of the iodophenylmethylthiocarbamide in chloroform, followed by reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia in the usual way, separated from alcohol in small white prisms, m.p. 219°. (Found: S, 11·2. $C_8H_7N_2IS$ requires S, 11·0 per cent.). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating a solution of the methyl-amino-base in acetic anhydride for a few minutes, and diluting the resulting solution with alcohol, crystallised in white plates, m.p. 185°. (Found: S, 11·0. $C_{10}H_9ON_2IS$ requires S, 9·7 per cent.). The *picrate*, prepared by mixing acetone solutions of the base and picric acid, crystallised in fine yellow needles which had m.p. 245°. (Found: S, 6·3. $C_8H_7N_2IS$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires S, 6·2 per cent.).

Thiazole Derivatives.

The Bromination of 2:4-Dimethylthiazole, the Formation of 5-Bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole Hydropentabromide, and the Reduction of 5-Bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole.—Thioacetamide was most conveniently prepared in a pure condition by heating a mixture of acetamide and phosphorus pentasulphide in benzene on a water-bath, under a reflux for 30-40 minutes; the thioamide being

obtained by crystallisation of the benzene mother-liquors ; glistening yellow plates, m.p. 107° . 2:4 Dimethylthiazole was prepared as follows: 12 G. of thioacetamide were gradually added to 18 c.c. of warm monochloroacetone in a large flask ; the mixture was gently heated on a wire gauze, extracted with 200 c.c. of hot 10% hydrochloric acid, and the extract was basified and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution of the thiazole was dried by means of anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the ether was distilled off from a water-bath, using an efficient fractionating column. The residual oil (12 g.), b.p. $135-145^{\circ}$, on redistillation yielded pure 2:4-dimethylthiazole as a highly refractive oil, possessing a strong pyridine-like odour, b.p. $143-144^{\circ}/762$ mm. The *chloroplatinate* of this base, prepared in the usual way from a solution of the thiazole in dilute hydrochloric acid and a 5 per cent. solution of platinum tetrachloride, crystallised in orange needles, m.p. $230-232^{\circ}$ (decomp) on rapid heating. (Found : Pt, 31.0. Calc. Pt, 30.7 per cent.). Hantzsch recorded the m.p. of this compound as 215° (*Annalen*, 1839, 250, 257).

5-Bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole Hydropentabromide.—A solution of the dimethylthiazole (1.5 c.c., 2.5 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was cooled to $0-2^{\circ}$ and treated with 2 c.c. of bromine, when heat was evolved and the *hydropentabromide* crystallised on keeping the solution for a short time. This compound formed unstable, glistening red prisms which had m.p. $93-95^{\circ}$ (decomp. with softening at 90°) after rapid drying on porous earthenware in a vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 78.4 ; Br (labile), 47.0. C_5H_6NBrS , $HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br (total), 80.9 ; Br (labile), 53.9 per cent.] The estimation of labile bromine was carried out in the usual way, by dissolving the bromo-addition compound in chloroform, to which a drop or two of acetic acid had been added, and adding a strong aqueous solution of potassium iodide ; the iodine liberated on shaking the mixture being titrated with *N/20*-sodium thiosulphate. In this estimation, a pink colouration was observed just before the end-point, which on addition of thiosulphate became pale yellow and finally colourless. It is highly probable that this accounts for the fact that the amount of labile bromine is somewhat less than the calculated value for a hydropentabromide ; a small amount of the labile bromine in the compound, which is doubtless liberated as hypobromous acid, being absorbed in some oxidative reaction which produces a pink colouring matter. It may be noted that the amount of bromine used for the production of the hydropentabromide

in quite appreciably below that theoretically required, in the experiment just recorded. The same product was, however, also isolated in a similar experiment in which an excess of the halogen was employed.—1.5 c.c. of bromine was added to a solution of (0.6 c.c.) of the dimethylthiazole in chloroform (10 c.c.) at 0°. The hydropentabromide separated as a red oil, which crystallised after keeping at laboratory temperature for three days, forming red prisms which had m.p. 90-93°. (Found: Br (labile), 46.0 per cent.) The same compound was also prepared according to the following conditions.—A solution of the dimethylthiazole (1 g.) in chloroform (10 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1 c.c.) at 0° and the mixture was kept for 2 hours, when the hydropentabromide crystallised in large red prisms, m.p. 93-95°. [Found: Br (total), 79.0; Br (labile), 47.5 per cent.]

5-Bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole.—The hydropentabromide was added to sulphurous acid (saturated with SO₂ at 15°), when immediate reduction took place, and the mixture was basified with ammonia (*d* 0.880) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried with sodium sulphate, filtered, and the ether was removed through a fractionating column, and the residual oil was distilled. The *5-bromothiazole* formed a colourless, refractive oil, possessing a strong pyridine-like odor, b.p. 188-190°/745 mm. (Found: Br, 41.8. C₅H₆NBrS requires Br, 41.7 per cent.). *Reduction*. A mixture of the *5-bromothiazole*, granulated tin, and concentrated hydrochloric acid was warmed under reflux on a steam-bath, until a vigorous reaction set in. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and made strongly alkaline with 30 per cent. sodium hydroxide. Extraction of this mixture by ether, followed by removal of the ether on a steam-bath, yielded *2:4-dimethylthiazole* which was identified by its properties, and the properties and analysis of the chloroplatinate which was obtained from the oil in the usual way. (Found: Pt, 31.3 per cent.).

The Bromination of 2-p-Toluidino-4-methylthiazole, the Formation of 5-Bromo-2-p-toluidino-4-methylthiazole Hydrotribromide, and the Synthesis of 2-o-Bromo-p-toluidino-4-methylthiazole. (i) Synthesis of 2-p-Toluidino-4-methylthiazole from Monochloroacetone and p-Tolylthiocarbamide.—A mixture of 5 g. of *p*-tolylthiocarbamide and 4 c.c. of monochloroacetone was gently heated in a Geissler flask until a sudden reaction occurred; the heating was continued for a minute or two longer and the product was extracted with

100 c.c. of hot 15 per cent. hydrochloric acid. The extract was basified with sodium hydroxide and the thiazole base (6 g.) was recrystallised from methyl alcohol (animal charcoal), when it formed glistening needles, m.p. 127-28°. (Found: N, 13.9; S, 15.8. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2S$ requires N, 13.7; S, 15.7 per cent.). (ii) *Bromination*. A solution of 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (0.5 g.) in chloroform (7 c.c.) was cooled to 0° and treated with bromine (0.6 c.c.). The red solution obtained in this way, was concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when the hydrotribromide of 5-bromo-2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole crystallised in glistening orange-red prisms, which were collected on porous earthenware and dried in a vacuum, m.p. 128-129° (decomp. with effervescence). [Found: Br (total), 61.3; Br (labile), 25.0. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2BrS$, HBr (Br_2) requires Br (total), 61.1; Br (labile), 30.6 per cent.]. The low figure for labile bromine obtained by iodometric titration, is attributed to the error introduced by oxidation, alluded to in connection with the hydropentabromide of 5-bromo-2:4-dimethylthiazole. *Reduction*. The hydrotribromide (4 g.) was added to an excess of sulphurous acid, and sulphur dioxide was passed through the mixture till the reaction was complete. Basification and crystallisation of the product from alcohol, yielded a dark coloured product, which on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol (charcoal), yielded 5-bromo-2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylbenzthiazole in the form of glistening plates, m.p. 142-143°. (Found: Br, 28.5. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 28.3 per cent.) (iii) 2-*o*-Bromo-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole was obtained by condensing *o*-bromo-*p*-tolylthiocarbamide with an excess of monochloroacetone, under conditions similar to those employed in the case of 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole. Extraction of the condensation product with hydrochloric acid, followed by basification, yielded the thiazole as an oil which crystallised from methyl alcohol in needles, m.p. 84-85°. (Found: Br, 28.7. $C_{11}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 28.3 per cent.) This compound was much more soluble than the isomeric 5-bromo-2-*p*-toluidino-derivative already described.

The Methylation of 2-p-Toluidino-4-methylthiazole and the Synthesis of 2-p-Tolylmethylamino-4-methylthiazole and of 2-p-Tolylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole.—(i) A mixture of 2-*p*-toluidino-4-methylthiazole (2 g.) and methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was heated at 100° for ten hours, and the product was basified with warm 20 per cent. potassium hydroxide and extracted with chloroform. The basic product was dissolved in methyl alcohol and fractionally crystallised

under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. It appeared to consist solely of 2-*p*-tolylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole, which had m.p. 107° alone, and when mixed with the specimen synthesised from monochloroacetone and sym-*p*-tolylmethylthiocarbamide. The presence of the isomeric 2-*p*-tolylmethylamino-4-methylthiazole could not be detected. In a similar experiment in which the methylation product was not basified, the product consisted entirely of the *hydriodide* of 2-*p*-tolylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole, which crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 224-226°. (Found: I, 36·4. $C_{12}H_{14}N_2S$, HI requires I, 36·8 per cent.). (ii) A mixture of asym-*p*-tolylmethylthiocarbamide (3·2 g.) and monochloroacetone (2 c.c.) was heated until a violent reaction took place, and the product was extracted with hydrochloric acid. 2-*p*-Tolylmethylamino-4-methylthiazole, obtained by basification of the extracts, crystallised from methyl alcohol in glistening plates, m.p. 60°. (Found: S, 15·0. $C_{12}H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 14·7 per cent.). The solubility of this compound in methyl alcohol is considerably greater than that of the isomeric tolyliminomethyl-dihydrothiazole. (iii) A mixture of sym-*p*-tolylmethylthiocarbamide (4 g.) and monochloroacetone (2 c.c.) was heated until condensation took place, the product was extracted with hydrochloric acid, and the extracts were basified. On recrystallisation from methyl alcohol, 2-*p*-tolylimino-3:4-dimethyl-2:3-dihydrothiazole was obtained in small crystals, m.p. 107-108°. (Found: S, 14·9. $C_{12}H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 14·7 per cent.).

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